

Pre-Surgical Orthodontics - A Narrative Review

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Abstract

Orthodontic treatment plays a vital role in contemporary orthognathic surgery, ensuring proper alignment and functional occlusion post-surgery. Fixed orthodontic appliances are typically required to achieve ideal arch coordination and occlusal interdigitation. Effective treatment planning involves careful analysis of tooth movements in all three planes of space, using comprehensive clinical assessments and diagnostic records. Collaboration between the orthodontist and surgeon is essential for successful outcomes. Thorough documentation of the orthodontic plan is critical and should be readily accessible throughout treatment. This structured approach supports predictable and efficient progress, helping to achieve both functional and aesthetic goals in orthognathic treatment.

Keywords : Class II Malocclusion, Class III Malocclusion, Envelope of Discrepancy, Open-bite, Pre-surgical Orthodontics, Vertical Maxillary Deficiency, Vertical Maxillary Excess

Introduction

The term Orthognathic is derived from the Greek words "orthos," meaning straight, and "gnathos," meaning jaw. Orthognathic surgery refers to the surgical correction of facial skeletal components to restore proper anatomical and functional relationships in individuals with dentofacial and skeletal deformities.¹

A jaw discrepancy is usually involved in a severe malocclusion, and only 3 possible treatments exist:²

- **Growth Modification :** In children who are still growing, dentofacial orthopaedics can influence and redirect growth patterns to a certain degree.
- **Orthodontic Camouflage :** Skeletal deformities may be masked through dental compensation, known as orthodontic camouflage, although this often results in extended treatment durations.
- **Orthognathic Surgery :** Once skeletal growth is complete, the most effective approach to correcting dentoskeletal discrepancies is a combination of orthodontic treatment and surgical intervention.

For patients with orthodontic issues so severe that neither growth modification nor

camouflage is sufficient, jaw realignment or repositioning of dentoalveolar segments through surgery becomes the only viable option. In such cases, surgery is not a replacement for orthodontic care, but rather must be carefully integrated with orthodontic and other dental treatments to ensure successful and comprehensive outcomes.³

Historical Background

A precise chronological account of the development of orthognathic surgery is unattainable, as surgeons in various countries were independently, and at times simultaneously, pioneering different techniques to reposition the maxilla, mandible, and chin.⁴

1. Simon P. Hullihen

The earliest recorded surgical procedure that could be classified as 'orthognathic' was likely carried out by American surgeon Simon P. Hullihen (Figure 1a) in 1849. He documented the case of a 20-year-old female patient, 'Mary S' (Figure 1b), who developed a prognathic mandibular open bite deformity as a result of severe burns to her neck and chest at age 5, leading to scar contractures.⁴

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Figure 1: (a) Simon P. Hullahen, (b) Mary S, aged 20, female patient, first-known surgical correction of a prognathic mandibular open bite deformity developed a prognathic mandibular open bite deformity as a result of severe burns to her neck and chest at age 5, leading to scar contractures.

1. Edward H. Angle

In 1898, James Whipple described a long-term case involving 'Mr K,' noting a pronounced prognathism of the lower jaw and a visible gap between the first and second bicuspids. Two years earlier, in 1896, he had referred the patient to Edward H. Angle (Figure 2), who advised performing a double resection of the lower maxilla to correct the severe protrusion. The patient, however, chose not to proceed with the surgery.⁴

Figure 2: Edward H. Angle

1. Vilray Papin Blair

Vilray Papin Blair (Figure 3a), in 1897, carried out the first 'double resection of the mandible' on the patient who declined Angle's treatment approach. This procedure consisted parallel cuts in the premolar areas and removal of the bone segments using an extraoral approach, resulting in a bilateral ostectomy of the mandibular body, as depicted in Figure 3b. The bony segments were secured with copper wire interosseous ligatures. Four months later, Whipple placed gold crowns on the posterior teeth to 'improve the occlusion.' Angle later commented that a V-shaped section should have been used for postoperative stabilization along with cast gold splints (Figure 3c).⁴

Figure 3:(a) Vilray Papin Blair, (b)Blair's Mandibular Body Ostectomy undertaken in 1897 (c) Cast gold splints for post-operative fixation as suggested by Edward H. Angle.

1. Rodrigues Ottolengui

Rodrigues Ottolengui (Figure 4a), a prominent American dentist and orthodontist, criticized Angle's splint and proposed that a single template splint (Figure 4b) should be used instead. This splint would represent the planned postoperative dental occlusion and after the ostectomy the teeth are cemented to it.⁴

Figure 4: (a) Rodrigues Ottolengui (b) Single Template Splint

1. Max Ballin

Max Ballin (Figure 5a), a surgeon from Detroit (Michigan), suggested:⁴ 'I would recommend ... to extract the teeth, necessary to remove for the resection, first, and then wait some months until the extraction wound is completely healed and atrophy of the alveolar process on the place of extraction has taken place. Then the surgeon can proceed, as in our case; that is, excise a piece of the jaw without entering the oral cavity' (Figure 5b)

Figure 5:(a) Max Ballin (b)Ballin's paper from 1908

Orthodontic-orthognathic Treatment Objectives

To explain the major objectives to patients considering orthodontic-orthognathic treatment, the acronym FRESH (Figure 6) has proven to be useful as a guide:⁵

- F Function
- R Reliable, Realistic
- E Esthetics, Economic
- S Stability, Satisfaction
- H Health

Figure 6: Orthodontic-Orthognathic Treatment Objectives acronym as 'FRESH'

1. Function: The goal is to establish optimal

gnathologic parameters for the stomatognathic system, such as balanced bilateral posterior occlusal support, to ensure temporomandibular joint (TMJ) stability and health without symptoms, canine rise, and incisal guidance.⁵

2. Reliable: Treatment methods that have been scientifically proven to be highly effective and carry lower risks for achieving skeletal corrections include:⁵

- o The use of micro-screws as anchorage in non-surgical treatments.
- o Jaw surgery for treating sleep apnoea.
- o Rigid fixation techniques.

3. Realistic: A treatment plan designed to maximize the likelihood of fulfilling both the patient's and doctor's expectations.⁵

4. Esthetics: Assessing facial aesthetics involves evaluating both the profile and frontal views to achieve soft tissue harmony and optimal symmetry. Facial balance should be maintained not only at rest but also during speech and facial expressions, particularly when the patient is smiling.⁵

5. Economic: Financial concerns often hinder the ideal combined orthognathic–orthodontic treatment plan due to limited insurance coverage for orthodontic care and reduced benefits for orthognathic surgery.⁵

2. Stability: An essential aspect of successful treatment is achieving jaw and tooth positions that remain reasonably stable over time.⁵

3. Satisfaction: To ensure satisfaction for both the patient and provider, it is important to have open conversations about the potential limitations or drawbacks of the chosen treatment plan. Utilizing visualized treatment goals and computerized simulations can help guide and support both the patient and provider.⁵

4. Health: The aim of treatment plans is to address and improve diseased or nonfunctional aspects while preserving the healthy elements of the case. This involves promoting emotional well-being, supporting the comfort, function, and health of the Temporomandibular Joint (TMJ), and maintaining periodontally healthy tissues.⁵

Epker Envelope Of Discrepancy

'Envelope of discrepancy' (Figure 7) given by Proffit and Ackermann graphically illustrates the amount of change possible with various treatment approaches:⁶

- o **Inner circle:** Limits of orthodontic tooth movement alone.
- o **Middle circle:** Tooth movement combined with growth modification.

o Outer circle: Surgical correction

Figure 7: Amount of tooth movement possible – (a) Anterior region of Maxilla⁵, (b) Anterior region of Mandible⁵, (c) Posterior region of Maxilla⁵, and (d) Posterior region of Mandible⁷. The coloured zones illustrate the potential range and direction of tooth movement, as indicated by the arrows in the diagram. The pink zone represents movement achievable with orthodontics alone, the yellow zone includes orthodontics combined with orthopaedics, the green zone involves skeletal anchorage, and the blue zone encompasses any combination of these with orthognathic surgery. The green zone appears "fuzzy" due to limited reliable data, allowing only approximate estimations.

Need For Surgical Orthodontic Treatment

The 'envelope of discrepancy' demonstrates that teeth can be moved more easily in some directions than others at any age, with little change in movement limits over time.⁶ Growth modification is effective only during active growth periods. In children, growth modification allows for greater correction than tooth movement alone can provide in adults; for instance, certain conditions like a centimetre of overjet can be managed

orthodontically in children but often require surgery in adults. A problem in a child is considered too severe for orthodontic treatment alone if it cannot be corrected by combining growth modification and camouflage. For older individuals, when the jaw discrepancy is too large to be compensated for or masked by tooth movement alone, surgery is the only option to achieve a satisfactory outcome (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Selecting a treatment – (Group 1) Normal skeletal relationship, (Group 2) Mild to moderate skeletal discrepancy, and (Group 3) Moderate to severe skeletal discrepancy 2

Skeletal Class II Malocclusion: ⁶

- 7mm or more of anterior overjet is highly correlated with the presence of Skeletal Class II Malocclusion, which in turn results from mandibular deficiency in most patients.
- Excessive overjet and jaw deformity require surgical correction.

Skeletal Class III Malocclusion: ⁶

- Presence of Skeletal Class III Malocclusion can be estimated from reverse overjet.
- Growth modification or orthodontic camouflage is not successful where the mandible is prognathic.
- Orthodontic management of reverse overjet of about 3mm can be achieved, but severe cases require surgical maxillary advancement or mandibular setback or both.

Goals of Pre-surgical Orthodontic Treatment

To ensure that during surgery, there are no obstacles to placing the jaws in their proper positions, the goal of pre-surgical orthodontics is to establish compatible arch forms and align the teeth in each arch. Teeth should be within a half cusp of their final transverse position so that post-surgical occlusion does not lock them into a crossbite.⁶

- **Dental Compensation:** 'Natural compensation' refers to the partial adjustment of anterior tooth axial inclination in the opposite direction to counteract severe skeletal jaw discrepancies (Figure 9a).

- **Reverse Orthodontics:** In preparing for jaw surgery, deliberately making the occlusion worse initially is often necessary (Figure 9b).

Figure 9: (a) Dental Compensation (b) Reverse Orthodontics

Surgical Treatment Objective (STO)

Epker and Fish proposed the "Two Patient Concept," wherein a mock surgical procedure is conducted on the patient's dental casts, which are subsequently considered as representing a second patient. This approach enables the orthodontist to evaluate the necessity of a pre-surgical orthodontic phase and, if already completed, to determine whether any additional corrections are required prior to surgery or can be effectively addressed during the post-surgical orthodontic phase.⁸

The postsurgical appearance of a patient can be reasonably predicted using cephalometric analysis. This technique, referred to as the 'surgical-treatment objective' (STO) or 'prediction tracing,' provides a two-dimensional visual representation of the expected changes in skeletal, dental, and soft tissue structures resulting from combined orthodontic treatment and orthognathic surgery to correct dentofacial and occlusal abnormalities.⁹

Various methods for STO prediction:¹⁰

- 1. Manual Tracing Method:** Traditional method using acetate tracing paper over a lateral cephalometric radiograph to simulate skeletal, dental, and soft tissue movements manually.
- 2. Template Prediction Method:** Uses transparent templates representing surgical movements (e.g., mandibular advancement or maxillary impaction) overlaid on cephalometric tracings to estimate postsurgical outcomes.
- 3. Photographic Prediction:** Combines lateral facial photographs with cephalometric tracings to visually estimate soft tissue changes after surgery.
- 4. Computer-Assisted Prediction:** Digital software simulates surgical movements and predicts both hard and soft tissue changes with greater accuracy and visual clarity.
- 5. Model Mock Surgery (Two Patient Concept):** Involves performing mock surgery on mounted dental

casts to plan and assess the surgical outcome and its orthodontic implications.

Treatment Planning For Surgical-orthodontic Treatment

1. Surgical Changes In Width Of Maxilla:

Surgically, it is possible to narrow or widen the maxilla. Narrowing the maxilla is technically difficult because it is necessary to remove bone to bring the 2 sides closer together, but this movement is entirely feasible (Figure 10a). At the extreme, the maxilla can be widened or narrowed perhaps 15mm, but 10mm of change is a more reasonable expectation. When the maxilla is widened surgically, there is considerable relapse tendency, which is expressed in 2 ways:⁶

a. Skeletal Relapse: Even when a bone graft is used to fill the gap and tooth position is preserved, the two halves of the maxilla tend to relapse and move back together after surgery.

b. Dental Relapse: Tendency of teeth to return to their original position after fixation is released.

Combination of these two effects leads to approximately 40% decrease in intermolar width that was established at surgery.

2. Surgical Changes In Width Of Mandible:

Changes in mandibular width are not as easy to make. There are 2 major limitations: (a) Soft tissue envelope and (b) TMJ. It is possible to narrow the mandible anteriorly and to widen or narrow the alveolar process somewhat posteriorly (Figure 10b). However, it is not possible to significantly widen the mandible or the dental arch anteriorly.⁶

3. Surgical Anteroposterior And Vertical Changes Of Maxilla:

Although movements in both directions are possible, they are not equally feasible (Figure 10c). The maxilla can be repositioned superiorly by 10-15mm with excellent stability and advanced by 10mm with good stability. The major limitation to moving the maxilla forward is the resistance of soft tissue anterior to it. Primarily, the upper lip makes advancing the maxilla difficult; the tighter the lip greater the resistance. The entire maxillary dentition can be moved backward surgically, but posterior bone interference limits this, and the maximum is only 3-5mm. Instead, the objective can be to retract the protruding anterior portion, and this can be accomplished by sectioning the maxilla and removing bone across the palate. Then the anterior segment can be brought back posteriorly while the posterior segments remain in position or move

anteriorly. Moving the entire maxilla down is technically feasible, although an interpositional bone graft is required. This movement is difficult as it is not stable post-surgically, because the maxilla tends to move back up due to the stretch of soft tissue created when the maxilla is repositioned in a downward direction. When the maxilla is moved up, it does not tend to come back down and indeed is remarkably stable in its superior position.⁶

4. Surgical Anteroposterior And Vertical Changes Of Mandible:

The inferior border or chin can be repositioned upward or downward, while the mandible can be advanced or set back. The gonial angle region can be elevated, although lowering it presents more of a challenge. When repositioning the mandible forward or backward, there are three potential options for vertical reorientation:⁶

a. The mandibular plane can increase as the gonial angle moves up and/or the chin moves down.

b. It can remain approximately the same as the mandible is repositioned along the existing mandibular plane.

c. It can decrease as the chin moves up and the gonial angle moves down.

Mandibular surgery that rotates the mandible down anteriorly and up posteriorly has excellent stability. Surgical movements along the existing mandibular plane, particularly advancements, are not as stable but are still acceptable. Surgery that rotates the mandible up anteriorly and down posteriorly is notoriously unstable and should be avoided whenever possible (Figure 10d).⁶

5. Dental-alveolar Surgery:

Surgical repositioning of dentoalveolar segments can be performed in all three planes of space. There are some limitations on the distance that the segments can be moved and on the size of the segments themselves (Figure 10e). As a general rule, the distance that the dentoalveolar segment can be moved surgically is approximately the same as the distance that teeth could be moved orthodontically.⁶

6. Chin Surgery:

Using an inferior border osteotomy, the chin can be repositioned in all three planes of space. Asymmetries can be corrected by shifting the chin sideways or adjusting its vertical position. A deficient chin can be advanced or moved downward, while an excessive projection can be corrected by repositioning it upward

or backward (Figure 9f).⁶

There are two primary methods to alter chin position:

1. Repositioning it through an inferior border osteotomy.
2. Augmenting it with additional materials such as bone, cartilage, or other alloplastic substances.

Figure 10: Surgical Changes – (a) Width of Maxilla, (b) Width of Mandible, (c) Anteroposterior and Vertical of Maxilla, (d) Anteroposterior and Vertical of Mandible, (e) Dentoalveolar Surgery, and (f) Chin Surgery⁵

Diagnosis And Treatment Of Specific Dentofacial Deformities

I. Anteroposterior Mandibular Deficiency:

Class II Div 1 Malocclusion¹¹

Clinical Characteristics : Profile View	Clinical Characteristics: Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retruded chin Chin-to-throat length is reduced Convex profile Everted lower lip Short and protrusive upper lip Deep mentolabial sulcus Nose appear large due to deficient mandible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appearance of double chin Deep labiomental fold Everted lower lip 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased overjet Accentuated Curve of Spee Increased overbite Tendency for maxillary incisor spacing Crowding in mandibular incisors

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure¹²

1. Level and align the maxillary and mandibular arches
2. Establish appropriate anteroposterior and vertical incisor positions
3. Establish arch compatibility-
 - o Correct inter-canine width.
 - o Mandibular second molars must be banded.
 - o Similar maxillary and mandibular archforms should be established.

a. Crowded Cases – Maxillary Arch

- Second premolars should be extracted.

b. Crowded Cases – Mandibular Arch

- In cases with crowding, accentuated Curve of Spee, and need for mandibular incisor retraction, first premolars should be extracted.
- In case of less anteroposterior space requirement, second premolars should be extracted.

c. Non-Crowded Cases

- Minimal crowding and mild spacing, a non-extraction approach is recommended.
- Class III mechanics is mandatory.

2. Class II Div 2 Malocclusion¹¹

Clinical Characteristics: Profile View	Clinical Characteristics: Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short lower facial height Low mandibular plane angle Lower lip appears deficient Pronounced chin button Deep mentolabial sulcus Mandible appears square 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Face appears short due to decreased vertical height Deep labiomental fold 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excessive Curve of Spee Deep overbite Maxillary lateral incisors are retrorotated Maxillary central incisors are labially flared

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure¹¹

a. Maxillary Arch

- To achieve sufficient overjet, a proper arch form, and adequate lip support, it is important to labially tip the maxillary incisors.

b. Mandibular Arch

- Curve of Spee should be levelled post-surgically.
- In severe deep-bite cases, it may be difficult to level the Curve of Spee.
- The anterior part of mandible is advanced downward and forward to create Class I Incisor relationship, while lower anterior facial height is increased.

II. Anteroposterior Mandibular Excess:

1. Class III Malocclusion¹¹

Clinical Characteristics : Profile View	Clinical Characteristics: Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inferior border of mandible is well-defined Long chin-throat angle Lip-chin-throat angle is acute Protrusive mandible Reduced labiomental fold 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chin button is not prominent Chin is often asymmetrical Lower third of face appears flat Reduced labiomental fold 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dental midline discrepancy Anterior and posterior crossbites with Class III malocclusion Mandibular incisors are lingually inclined Generalized interdental spacing and flared incisors, with anterior open-bite, suggest a large tongue

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure²

1. Eliminate anterior and posterior dental compensation.
2. Establish appropriate anteroposterior and vertical incisor positions.
3. Achieve compatible archforms and inter-canine width.
4. Correct tooth size discrepancy problems.
5. If mandibular asymmetry is present, dental midline should be placed in midline of chin.
6. If chin deformity is present, dental midline change is not necessary as genioplasty will correct the chin position.

a. Maxillary Arch

- After dental decompensation and levelling, Class II elastics may be used to advance the mandibular buccal segments and procline the mandibular incisors.

b. Mandibular Arch

- Maxillary incisor region should be applied with high-pull headgear.
- Aids in retraction and prevention of extrusion and proclination of maxillary incisors.

III. Anteroposterior Maxillary Deficiency:

1. Class III Malocclusion¹¹

Clinical Characteristics: Profile View	Clinical Characteristics: Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cheeks appear sunken Upper lip appears flat and reduced in length Lower lip and chin in balance with nose 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cheeks appear sunken Sclera seen inferiorly of the iris of the eye Short and flat upper lip Alar base is narrow Paranasal flattening 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Class III malocclusion Crowding in maxillary arch Small or absent maxillary lateral incisors Normal inclination of mandibular incisors Narrow maxillary arch with lingual crossbite

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure²

1. Correct existing dental compensations
2. Achieve ideal positioning of incisors
3. Align and level both arches
4. Ensure coordination between maxillary and mandibular arches.

a. Crowded Maxillary Arch

- Significant crowding and maximum retraction are necessary; extraction of first premolars is indicated
- Mild crowding and minimal retraction are necessary; extraction of second premolars is indicated.

b. Crowded Mandibular Arch

- Advancement of the mandibular incisors may be limited by thin alveolar bone and/or lack of attached gingiva
- Extraction of second premolar is indicated.

c. Common Extraction Pattern

- Extraction of first premolars in the maxillary arch
- Extraction of first premolars in the maxillary arch and second premolars in the mandibular arch

IV. Anteroposterior Maxillary Excess:²

Clinical Characteristics : Profile View	Clinical Characteristics : Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protrusion of middle third of face • Prominent infra-orbital rims and cheekbones • Short and everted upper lip • Deep labiomental sulcus • Lip incompetence • Acute nasolabial angle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased lower facial height • Prominent middle third of face • Lip incompetence • Maxillary incisors trap the lower lip • Short and everted upper lip 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tendency toward open bite • Palatal vault is high-arched • Constricted and narrow maxillary arch

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure²

1. Brackets on teeth adjacent to proposed interdental osteotomies are bonded such that root divergence can be achieved.
2. Maxillary canine brackets can be switched from right to left and vice versa.
3. After surgery is completed, these brackets are replaced with the correct brackets.

v. Vertical Maxillary Deficiency:²

Clinical Characteristics : Profile View	Clinical Characteristics: Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced height of the lower facial third and the middle facial third • Acute nasolabial angle • Chin appears excessive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Face appears short and square • Reduced maxillary incisors exposure under upper lip • With the mandible closed, skin folds lateral to the oral commissure become apparent with turned down corners of the mouth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased interocclusal freeway space • Class III dental relationship • Mandibular overclosure resulting in bruxism and attrition

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure²

1. Cephalometric radiographs should be taken before treatment, with the lips gently touching and mandible in a resting position.
2. Repositioning of the maxilla in forward and downward direction to increase the vertical height should not exceed the available freeway space.

a. Crowded Arches

- Severe crowding is present, extraction of first premolars is indicated.
- Mild crowding is present, extraction of second premolars is indicated.

b. Maxillary Advancement

- Large maxillary advancement is needed and crowding is present, maxillary first premolars and mandibular second premolars extraction is indicated to create a large crossbite.

c. Transverse Maxillary Deficiency

- Correct it Surgically

VI. Vertical Maxillary Excess:¹³

Clinical Characteristics : Profile View	Clinical Characteristics: Frontal View	Dental Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased mandibular plane angle • Mandible rotated downward and backward • Increased interlabial distance • Increased maxillary incisor exposure • Increased lower facial height 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower facial height increased • Decreased upper facial height to total facial height • Increased anterior facial height • Increased interlabial distance • Increased maxillary incisor exposure • Gummy smile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-arched palate • V-shaped maxillary arch • Tendency for anterior open bite present • Maxillary teeth are in a palatal crossbite • Over-eruption of mandibular incisors resulting in increased Curve of Spee • Mandibular incisors are upright and crowded

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure²

a. Mandibular Arch

- Level, align, close all spaces, and achieve good arch form.
- Depending on the case, extractions along with Class II or Class III mechanics will be necessary.

b. Maxillary Arch

1. Brackets on teeth adjacent to proposed interdental osteotomies are bonded such that root divergence can be achieved.
2. Maxillary canine brackets can be switched from right to left and vice versa.
3. After surgery is completed, these brackets are replaced with the correct brackets.

III. Open Bite Deformities:

1. Class I Open Bite²

Clinical Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posterior vertical maxillary excess • Mandible rotated clockwise • Increased interlabial gap • Increased maxillary incisor exposure • Often, transverse maxillary deficiency • Could be Skeletal Class I due to rotation from Class III

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure

a. Segmental Arch Mechanics

- Dual occlusal plane of maxilla.
- Avoid orthodontic extrusion of anterior teeth.

b. Continuous Arch Mechanics

- Single occlusal plane of maxilla

c. Extraction Vs Nonextraction

- Influenced by 2 factors:
 - o Crowding
 - o Anteroposterior position of mandibular incisors.

2. Class II Open Bite²

Clinical Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased lower facial height • Recessive chin • Vertical maxillary excess • Increased interlabial gap • Skeletal Class II relationship • Could be Skeletal Class II due to rotation from Class I • Increased mandibular plane angle • Transverse maxillary deficiency (posterior crossbite) • Increased maxillary incisor exposure under the upper lip

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure

1. Level and align the maxillary and mandibular teeth on the basal bone.
2. Achieve arch coordination of the maxillary and mandibular arches.
3. Expand buccal segments only where teeth are palatally inclined to the basal bone.
4. In case of segmental osteotomy, deviate the roots at the intended osteotomy areas.

3. Class III Open Bite²

Clinical Characteristics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandibular anteroposterior excess, with backward rotation of mandible • Maxillary vertical excess – more posterior than anterior • Transverse maxillary deficiency • Posterior crossbites • Class III malocclusion • Often, reverse Curve of Spee • Increased mandibular plane angle

Pre-Surgical Orthodontic Procedure¹²

1. Eliminate dental compensation.
2. Level and align the maxillary arch in segments and align the mandibular arch.
3. In case of segmental osteotomy, deviate the roots at the intended osteotomy areas.

Wire Sequence

WIRE (Dimension in mils)	PROPERTIES
16 NITI (austenite/superelastic)	Outstanding load-deflection characteristics
16 NITI (martensite)	Obsolete for initial alignment, but still valuable as an intermediate wire
17.5 twist steel	Economical with good properties
19.5 coaxial steel	Properties similar to 17.5 twist steel, but higher cost
14 steel with loops	Excellent properties, but requires time for fabrication

Table 1: Properties of wires used during the Pre-surgical Orthodontic Stage.⁶

0.018" slot	0.022" slot
16 NITI (austenite) or 14 steel loops (asymmetric crowding)	17.5 twist steel or 16 NITI (austenite) (severe crowding)
16 steel	16 steel, 18 steel
17x25 TMA	21x25 TMA
17x25 steel	21x25 steel

Table 2: Wire sequence in 0.018" and 0.022" slot brackets.⁶

Time Estimates For Surgical-Orthodontic Treatment

Stage of Treatment	Time Required	Variations In Treatment Time
1. Presurgical orthodontics	2 to 12 months	Varies with the difficulty of alignment
2. Surgery/Hospitalization	2 to 6 days	Typically, 3 to 4 days
3. Under surgeon's care before beginning postsurgical orthodontics	3 to 8 weeks	Reduced with rigid fixation (3 to 5 weeks) as compared with maxillomandibular fixation (5 to 8 weeks)
4. Postsurgical orthodontics	3 to 6 months	Over 6 months indicates a problem or inadequate preparation

Table 3: Time estimates for Surgical-Orthodontic Treatment.⁶

Conclusion

Presurgical orthodontics aims to align the teeth with the basal bone, ensure compatibility between the arches, and position the incisors correctly in both the anteroposterior and vertical dimensions. This stage plays a vital role, as poor preparation of tooth alignment and arch form can compromise the efficiency

of orthognathic surgery and lengthen the post-surgical phase. Conversely, extending the duration of presurgical orthodontics may unnecessarily increase overall treatment time without offering substantial advantages to the patient.

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